

Social Media Use and Social Endurance: Analysis of Social and Psychological Factors

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Abstract

The concept of social networking originated as a new information channel for internet connections around the world, enabling communities to connect. College students use multiple internet and social media channels, including networking sites, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter that are used to establish connections and share information about everyday life. Ninety percent of undergraduate students have their own Facebook account and spend more than two hours daily using this app for social connections. Other social networking sites are also used in the highest proportion by youngsters, including graduate and undergraduate students. The present study aimed to explore the social media use affects the social endurance of individuals in society. Moreover, it aimed to qualitatively analyze the social and psychological factors among individuals in society using social media networks that influence the level of social endurance. Positivism philosophy and inductive approach through exploratory research design were used under qualitative research method to investigate the concept of the influence of social media on social endurance. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect in-depth interviews from 15 participants who were university students. The in-depth interviews were conducted using a structured interview guide consisting of thirty-one exploratory questions addressing the influential phenomenon of social media effects through a structured interview guide. The major findings of the study reveal the significant positive influence of social media on social endurance. However, the influence of social media may vary from individual to individual based on its usage experiences. Interpersonal communication, social interactions, self-esteem, and level of confidence are social and psychological factors affecting social endurance using social life, lifestyle, social standards, social relations, communication, and social endurance.

Keywords: *Social Life, Lifestyle, Social Standards, Social Relations, Social Endurance.*

Introduction

Social media is defined as the electronic channels used by community members to connect or to develop online communication to inform or share information, ideas, and personal content (audio as well videos) with others through the medium of social media (Fortes, Lima-Junior, Ferreira & Fonseca, 2022). Twitter, Instagram, and many others. Social media is the third

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latest and most advanced type of media it depends on more advanced technological devices and the internet. With the potential to have both beneficial and detrimental effects on social endurance, electronic communication has become an essential component of contemporary living.

The most popular types of media are social media and have the maximum number of users in the whole globe (Agnihotri, Kulshreshtha & Tripathi,2021). There is no doubt social media influences individuals' lives in many ways and changes their lives according to the modern or developed lifestyle. Social media improves the capacity to establish and preserve connections by enabling communication across long distances and offering venues for community involvement. It acts as a digital platform for networking, particularly for people who are lonely or have restricted access to real-world social networks. This has helped build emotional resilience and a feeling of community. People who participate in online communities frequently discover assistance that can improve their social endurance and help them deal with obstacles in life (Fernández & Cachán-Cruz,2022).

Social media has the power to influence our social standards; lifestyle and social relations. It also changes individuals' behaviors and attitudes. Prior or previous research explains the influence of social media influence on individuals by two major effects; on individuals privately and through public (Dewi, Pradana, Nugraha& Adiputri,2021).

Social media usage is increasing day by day very quickly and individuals accept all social changes. Several companies use social media to influence individuals through awareness about their brands, selling inventories, and customer engagement. Advanced information and communication have changed individuals rapidly lives and social relations (Zhou, Mou, Wang & Wu,2021). With the arrival of social media worldwide, many individuals have up activities in terms of usage or utilization the social media wisely for more acquisition of knowledge meanwhile, many dedicate of the utilization of most of their time to many activities that are not valuable for their academic-related such as nonstop share their pictures, videos and other important contents on different social sites von (Schönfeld & Tan,2021).

In simple words, social media refers to online devices that are developed for many objectives of interaction, communication, sharing information, and personal content

Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

(Zuckerberg, 2015). Influence of social media on our family relations, social interactions, lifestyle, and social relations in many ways in our society(Mpofu,2021). Present time social media has developed our lives and relations, especially our young generation very quickly on modern patterns of life in every society in around the whole world (Mpofu, 2021). Nevertheless, due to its growing or developing and global reach, social media's relation to interaction, and interaction of the ethical minorities in our societies is a under research field (Buckley, Gainous & Wagner,2021).

However, as both culture and technology have advanced, it has become increasingly important to study the connections between online platform use and people integration to comprehend the social ramifications of consumers of social media as they integrate and interact with others (Wegner,2021). The availability of the internet and smartphones enable a participant to stay online and connected whenever he wants. Despite the emergence of new technologies and services for human beings its relation to the incorporation of traditional sections into civilization is still the focus of Manny researchers. Numerous studies have been done to evaluate the effects of social media from various perspectives (Wegner,2021).

The capacity or power to go on or final, particularly despite fatigue, stress, or other worst and worst conditions or stamina of any individual (Scott, Haycraft & Plateau,2021). Endurance is defined as the self-resilience, efficacy, and capacity of an individual or organization to exert to maintain efforts against challenges (Scott, Haycraft & Plateau,2021). Endurance is often invoked as something that individuals and society should desire, especially given that diversity in all its types is increasingly a feature of present-day democracies. When tension and stress arise, some leaders call for endurance and generation endurance of particular groups or encourage common efforts to become, a “more enduring society (Bollinger, Bartel, Küper, Weber & Gehlen,2021).

In 2004, Secretary General of the UN, Kofi Annan, “Endurance intercultural dialogue and respect for diversity are more compulsory than ever in a world where peoples are becoming more and more closely interconnected (Zhou & Mou,2021). One another example according to UNESCO Director-General Audrey Azoulay, we have to develop and practice persistence as a human virtue every time it binds us together. Young women may be more vulnerable to

problems with body image due to a variety of societal and personal characteristics. (Sarasvathy, 2021).

One could legitimately argue that the reasons that place adolescent girls and young women vulnerable to body image issues include low self-esteem, persistent sadness, and body insecurities. Women should be educated about the importance of appearance and self-worth (Iqbal, Alghadir & Anwer, 2021). Several theories support the idea that individual differences influence body image dynamics. Reviews provide empirically derived and conceptually based explanations for the influence of bodily attributes and the impacts of these specific components on body image problems (Zimanyi, Wolff & Schüler, 2021).

Therefore, when an individual reaches their maximum or minimum ideal absorption or when attractiveness plays a significant role in their self-esteem it affects how they display their body image (Bimbova, Bacova, Kisucka & Lukacova, 2022). As considered viewpoints on media revealed through social networking functions and pleasures affect the ideological and behavioral consequences of a specific individual. Social comparisons and psychological processes usually serve as moderators in the relationship between social media use and body image issues (Valkenburg et al., 2013).

According to comprehensive literature by Naslund et al. (2020), social media platforms allow people to stay in touch even when they live far away. This study focused on the review, of those who are lonely, such as senior citizens or people with long-term medical conditions, who can participate in online groups that provide financial and emotional assistance, which will help them stay socially resilient during trying times. Social media platforms and digital platforms for networking, particularly for people who are lonely or have restricted access to real-world social networks. This has helped build emotional resilience and a feeling of community. It is concluded that people who participate in online communities frequently discover assistance that can improve their social endurance and help them deal with obstacles in life.

Another longitudinal investigation by Ellison et al. (2018), illustrated the importance of social media as its uses promote the development of cultural capital that bridges and strengthens bonds. People may obtain resources and assistance through these varied networks, which promotes adaptability and durability in social settings. They concluded that users become more

Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

adaptive in social settings and more tolerant of social shocks because of this capacity to develop both bonding and linking social capital. Furthermore, social media platforms specialist communities give underrepresented groups a forum for self-expression and camaraderie, both of which enhance psychological health.

LaRose (2014) investigated how online interactions help people to feel connected and like they belong, especially for underrepresented groups. According to the study, joining specialized groups can improve a person's social endurance by assisting them in overcoming social pressures. Because people miss out on opportunities to cultivate critical interpersonal abilities, this decline frequently erodes the resilience needed to handle social issues in the real world. Additionally, overusing social media can result in social fatigue, typified by the overpowering sensation of always being "plugged in." This frequently leads to a lack of emotional stamina for significant offline and online connections.

According to a meta-analysis by Zhou & Wang (2022), excessive online platform use is linked to a decline in meaningful, in-person relationships. Overall psychological resilience is weakened as a result, frequently leading to a decline in the capacity to settle disputes or sustain long-lasting offline connections. In a review of the detrimental effects of online presence on self-esteem, Fardouly et al. (2018) found exacerbates anxiety and despair, making it harder for people to deal with social difficulties. People's ability to sustain positive social interactions is impacted by this psychological pressure since they become more fixated on their alleged flaws. Because of the continual barrage of comments, likes, and shares, emotional control also becomes difficult, leading to a need for outside approval. Over time, such actions might weaken social endurance by causing worry and a brittle sense of self-worth.

The enduring psychological repercussions of cyberbullying were examined by Hinduja & Patchin (2020). According to the research, people who experience online harassment frequently display withdrawal symptoms, which weaken their social resilience and make it more difficult for them to build wholesome connections. According to a review of 15 research, Keles, McCrae, and Grealish (2020) found that an over-reliance on likes and comments as a form of social reinforcement creates unease. Because of this dependence, users become too susceptible to

criticism from others, which weakens resistance. Internet platforms' transparency and anonymity frequently increase a person's vulnerability to abuse. Withdrawal behaviors are common among victims of cyberbullying, and they can undermine their self-esteem and capacity to build lasting connections. Long-term consequences of this kind of psychological strain may include a further decline in social endurance.

Considering these obstacles, there are ways to lessen social media's drawbacks and maximize its positive aspects. People have found that taking planned vacations from social media, known as "digital detoxes," helps them reestablish offline connections and lessen their reliance on online communication. In addition to improving the quality of connections, mindful social media use which entails restricted and intentional engagement can lessen the emotional toll that excessive use takes.

The provided surveys, discussion forums, and analyzed social networks were among the qualitative and quantitative techniques typically used in these systematic evaluations. A comprehensive grasp of the multiple impacts of social media is provided by the emphasis on a variety of demographics, including pupils, employees, and marginalized groups. The use of self-reported data and different definitions of social durability in different research are drawbacks stating that Social media has ramifications for social endurance that are both favorable and harmful. Although it offers forums for support and connection, excessive use and abuse can weaken emotional fortitude and the capacity to sustain deep connections. People may optimize social media's positive impacts while reducing its negative ones by embracing mindful practices and placing a higher value on in-person relationships. Fostering healthy social situations in a world that is becoming increasingly digital requires an understanding of these processes.

Aim and Research Questions

In the current digital era, when social media significantly influences people's social life and mental health, "Analysis of Social and Psychological indicators are proving particularly pertinent. By looking at social and psychological aspects, this study seeks to understand how social media use affects social endurance, or the capacity to manage and negotiate social interactions and demands. Addressing these dynamics can provide light on how social media impacts associations, self-esteem, and social behaviors, which is important given the rising worry about the negative consequences of excessive social media usage on mental health.

Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

Understanding the concept of the influence of social media on social lives and its impacts on social endurance was the major aim of the study. The research tends to explore the influence of social media as a significant factor it influences on social endurance through study. It also identified the influence of social media that has changed the social endurance of individuals in their social lives. This study seeks to understand the influence of social media on social endurance in the contemporary Pakistani context. The following research questions were made to explore through the study.

- How does social media influence an individual's perceptions of life life style, a perspective of life?
- How does social media influence social endurance?
- How does social endurance influence through social and psychological factors of an individual's life?

Methodology

Participants

A total of fifteen (15) (n1=7, n2=8) student participants from the Department of Mass Communication were selected using convenient sampling within the group structure. Both male and female participants of postgraduate students having an age range of twenty to twenty-five (20-25) years of age were selected. A convenient approach to selecting a sample was preferred in the present study. Participants both males and females either married, unmarried, separated, divorced, or widowed were selected. Exploratory research design was used under the qualitative research paradigm to explore the phenomenon of social endurance and its factors (social and psychological).

Measures

Agreement Form, Sheet for Research Information, and Demographic Form: An information sheet that consisted research topic, purpose, procedure, and ethical issues was used that showed a willingness to participate in the present study. The demographic sheet consisted of age, gender, education, and usage of social media tendencies were measure. The information sheet was used to brief the research participants about the purpose and process that the researcher used to evaluate the results of the study. The participants were also informed about the

importance of their participation in research and how their verbatim are essential to making themes and sub-themes of the study. Students took taken consent form to ensure their participation and views about career choice would be kept confidential and only be used for research purposes.

Interview Guide: An interview guide was used in to interview process containing all the questions addressing the effectiveness of the influence of social media on the endurance of students. All the perspectives of psychological, social, and personal perceptions about social media content choice and social perspectives affecting their social endurance level were asked in the interview guide. A total of twenty-five (25) questions measuring the effects of different aspects of social media were asked. An information sheet was used to inform participants about the purpose of conducting the research study and the purpose of their involvement in research was informed before enrolling them in semi-structured interviews.

Table No.1: *Personal characteristics of participants or demographic sheet.*

Participant	Gender	Age	Academic Qualification	Year/semester	Unit/Department
1	Female	22	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
2	Male	23	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
3	Male	25	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
4	Female	21	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
5	Male	24	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
6	Female	22	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
7	Female	21	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
8	Male	21	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
9	Male	24	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
10	Male	24	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
11	Male	22	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
12	Male	25	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
13	Female	21	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
14	Female	24	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University
15	Female	25	Mass Communication	MSc	Punjab University

Data Analysis

The process of data analysis started with coding data to analyze through thematic analysis. Up until saturation was reached, the researcher kept on collecting the data. To fully comprehend the significance of the collected interviews, the researchers listened to the tapes several times. The main raw data from each interview was put together in the form of codes. Before creating the narrative by linking the codes based on the participants' answers, links between the codes were established to form sub-themes. Within the participant replies, recurring trends and themes were found. Key topics that were pertinent to the study's goals were emphasized in the results.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.1: *Characteristics of individual's geographic information (N=15)*

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD
Gender	Male	8	56.7.2%		
	Female	7	46.3%		
Age	20-22	6	42.8%	2.87	.361
	23-25	6	42.8%		
	24-25	3	14.2%		
Education	MSc	6	42%		
	MSc	6	42%		
	MSc	3	14.2%		
Belonging Area	Urban	10	71%		
	Rural	5	29%		
Religion	Muslim	12	85.7%		
	Non-Muslim	3	14.2%		
Monthly Income	20,000Rs-50,000Rs	3	14.2%		
	60,000Rs_80,000Rs	6	29.3%		
	above 1 Lac	6	29.3%		

Note. f= frequency, %= percentage

Thematic Analysis

Codes

Participants used social media for useful purposes like communication, information, and productive ways. Social media improves their life and it's used in better ways. The perception of participants related to the influence of social media on social interaction will be described. As one of the participants said:

"The influence of social media depends on the users they can use it in positive or productive ways and negative or wastage of time. He says that the majority of our new generation of social media users negatively use social media as compared to positive or productive ways. He also says that social media plays a vital role in social interaction with individuals, known and unknown individuals this influence is expended worldwide"

- More time spend to use social media
- Communication
- Entertainment
- Information purposes

Perceptions of participants will be described by the influence of social media on social standards. Five respondents (three female and two male) quoted,

" According to the influence of social media on our social standards are many ways and influence on social standards change their societal values, beliefs, and social pattern of individuals very quickly for their lives. Lifestyle, living standards, and behaving patterns are changing very rapidly from societies".

By reviewing the transcripts for effects on personal perceptions and experience of social media users.

- Increase great of opportunities or choice
- Changed belief systems and perceptions of different phenomenon
- Change in social standards

Despite its elevated rank and undeniable worth, the influence of social media on time and money spent is a phenomenon. Almost all participants say that the influence of social media on time and money spent is more than other aspects of social life.

Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

According to some of the participants, “They spend more than six hours daily on social media apps and also more than fifteen hundred rupees on internet packages monthly to use social media”. From participants verbatim about the influence of social media given codes were developed;

Respondents shared their relative's experience saying, “Inthe modern world social media is a reliable and advanced resource of communication, connectivity and information sharing with others everywhere within country or worldwide”.

Based on the effects of social media on individuals’ lives following codes were developed;

- Acquired new Lifestyle
- Change in interests and preferences
- Source of advanced communication related to accessories
- Expand excessive money
- Wastage of time

Table No.3: *Emergence of sub-themes and major themes from the codes*

Codes	Sub-Themes	Major Themes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More time spend to use social media • Communication • Entertainment • Information purposes • Increase great of opportunities or choice • Changed belief systems and perceptions of different phenomenon • Change in social standards • Expand excessive money • Wastage of time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning and Communication • Entertainment • Cultural values • Personal choices • Perceptual effects • Inhibiting social gathering • Impact on time and money 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Factors • Personal / Individual Factor • Negative impact on time and money • Economic Conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acquired new Lifestyle • Change in interests and preferences • Source of advanced communication related to accessories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effects on lifestyles • Dependency of gadgets 	

Initial themes

Initial themes evaluated by the researcher as:

- Social Factor
- learning and Communication
- Entertainment
- Cultural values
- Personal choices
- Perceptual effects Inhibiting social gathering
- Impact on time and money
- Effects on lifestyles
- Dependency of gadgets

Major Themes

- Social Factors
- Personal \ Individual Factor
- Negative impact on time and money
- Personal and Psychological Factors

Figure.1: Showing the connections between themes, and subthemes of the verbatim of participant's responses.

Figure.1:Initial thematic map showing six themes containing subthemes from the transcript coding.

Discussion

The present study found social factors one of the most effective factors of social media presentation. Communities’ responses to any incident or experience on social media platforms left long-lasting effects that reflected in individuals’ behavior and attitudes. The generalizability of thinking patterns and learned behavior from social media towards the common population of a community is found to be increased over time. Danger to legal rights and risk factors are the most common factors affecting the social values of individuals influenced through social media. This legal risk usually comes from social media medium used by individuals. Many of the fake apps containing malicious viruses we use result in effects on our devices and gadgets (Uyun & Warsah, 2022).

Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

Another important legal risk is spoiling the individuals' rights by crossing the line between individual personal and professional life. Many of the workers on social media especially in TV dramas, documentaries, and short films may project their personal lives to work and take their work stress to their home which influences their presented content and performance which automatically affects the perception of their viewers (Giriskan, 2021). Personal content, pictures, videos, and other stuff related to academic certifications, professional experiences, personal affairs, marital statuses, and information about one's private informal life may have the risk of theft which results in negative social behavior i.e. bullying, threatening behaviors, and harassment (Piao, Shang, Yan, Hao & Gu, 2022).

These behaviors due to excessive use of social media and uploading affect social norms and ethics on a large scale. Credibility refers to time and money spent purchasing gadgets, network packages, availing offers, and earning from social media. Credibility also refers to the amount of time we spend on a daily and weekly basis to scroll down updates, share information, and increase our knowledge (Komarudin & Wali, 2022). The Genuineness of different channels and mediums of social media also reflects their credibility in the form of public interest and trust for their news, information, and knowledge of various circumstances.

Personal and individual factors include the internal and external well-being of individual figures at a personal level. Social media access is useful for students as they get help in their studies through various apps. Moreover, they get it easy to share their existing knowledge with their social groups through the usual of WhatsApp, Twitter, Messenger, and Facebook. Many websites and apps are now launching some courses for the young generation to increase their cognitive abilities through vocational training, clocking, sewing, computer courses, website development, and self-enhancing programs (Silva, Rizardi & Gomes, 2021).

Self-confidence, motivation, personal well-being, and self-worth. Along with the positive effects of social media use, there were many social factors affecting the perception at the individual level. Various set patterns of actions are taken by individuals to get fame on social media. Responses of the public to their content and performance may affect their confidence and they may develop loneliness, depression, anxiety, and long-lasting stress. The findings of the study have revealed that the influence of social media is undoubtedly on social endurance in the

form of personal attributes, interests, viewpoints, beliefs, psychological aspects, and social aspects associated with the effects of social media von (Schönfeld & Tan, 2021).

Conclusions

It was concluded that individuals' patterns of evaluating ethical, patriotic, political, cultural, traditional, communication, and religious perspectives are influenced by social media. Results indicate a higher ratio of women with high tendencies to watch social media than males. It's concluded that females are more obsessed with social media than males and have higher tendencies to be attracted to content being presented in social media addressing Ethical, Patriotic, Political, Cultural, Traditional, Communication, and religious perspectives. However, some respondents have different opinions on the above; according to the theme social endurance is important in individuals' lives but it does not affect the influence of social media. Social endurance is important for healthy and social dealing with others; especially when some think is not favorable or beneficial but while this individual endures.

Limited data was collected by approaching limited students which included the limitation of the study whereas, it was suggested to conduct a study to check the influences of social media in marketing as an influencer and individual buying behaviors along with social media effects on this department.

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Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

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Journal of Media Studies 39(1)

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